

Rethinking the use of antimicrobials in livestock production systems

Policy Brief n° 2

How to enable farmers to reduce antimicrobial use?

Lee-Ann Sutherland, Orla Shortall (The James Hutton Institute), Gareth Enticott (Cardiff University)

This contributes to the main goal of the project which is to analyse the practices and decision systems of farmers, veterinarians and other professionals involved in managing the health of farmed animals ; and to the specific objective of identifying levers/incentives for adherence to prudent use principles by veterinarians and farmers.

Europe is the world's third largest meat producer after China and the United States. Globally there is a major market trend to increase demand for animal proteins which directly translates with specific needs and requirements from the farming sector and linked policies. Antibiotic-free meat production trends is expected to regularly increase in the coming years.

This policy brief should be particularly relevant for farmers, as well as veterinarians and animal health professionals, from any European country.

OVERVIEW

The reduction of AMU at farm level is dependent on the decision-making and practical limitations of farm staff. The RoadMap project assessed farmers' practices and attitudes relating to antimicrobial use to identify what factors could hinder or foster more prudent use of antimicrobials.

Ten case studies were conducted, enrolling dairy, beef, poultry and pig herds across Europe, Mozambique and Vietnam.

Findings demonstrate that there are three broad patterns – often set at national level per commodity – of antimicrobial use: minimal or no antimicrobial use; restricted but necessary antimicrobial use; necessary and unrestricted use. Within these, farmers develop social norms associated with antimicrobial use. For example, for countries and sectors where minimal (if any) use was the norm (e.g. Sweden, Denmark), farmers expressed pride in not needing to use antimicrobials. In contrast, in countries and sectors where antimicrobial use was considered 'necessary' (e.g. France, Italy), antimicrobial use was recognised as part of keeping animals healthy and under certain circumstances could be considered part of good farming practice. In countries where antimicrobial use was largely unrestricted, farmers were often – but not always - aware that they should limit their antimicrobial use, but often had little incentive to do so.

In addition, changes to antimicrobial use often came about as part of broader transitions within the sector (e.g. regulatory shifts), procurement standards (e.g. labelling requirements) or upgrading of farm facilities. Major changes on farm – such as farm succession, accidents, investment in new facilities, low profitability – also influence antimicrobial use.

In this policy brief, we address how socialised norms of 'good farming', and broader 'triggers' for change can be mobilised to reduce antimicrobial use.

RELATED OUTPUTS

- Shortland, F., Shortall, O., Sutherland, L-A, Fortané N., Eberhart, J. (2022) *Roadmap deliverable 2.2 "Rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems in the management of animal production". Report on the results of qualitative and quantitative research on farmer practices.*
- Bâtie, C., Ha, Le Thi Thu, Loire, E., Truong, D.B., Tuan, H.M., Cuc, N.T.K, Paul, M., Goutard, F. 2022. Characterisation of chicken farms in Vietnam: A typology of antimicrobial use among different production systems. *Preventative Veterinary Medicine* 208: 105731.
- Enticott, G., O'Mahony, K., Shortall, O., Sutherland, L-A. (2022) 'Natural born carers'? Reconstituting gender identity in the labour of calf care. *Journal of Rural Studies* 95: 362-372

'Good farmers' care for their livestock

'Peer pressure' normalises expectations around AMU. Farmers see themselves – and want others to see them – as 'good farmers' who produce healthy livestock. Their care for their livestock reflects their skill.

Antimicrobial use is one of several practices which may – or may not – indicate 'good farming', depending on the broader expectations of the industry.

Farmers adapt their expectations of 'good farming' over time, in response to regulatory shifts.

Institute benchmarking to enable farmers to compare their AMU to similar farmers directly

Support participatory initiatives between farmers, supply chain and veterinarians to establish good practices.

Bundle AMU reduction measures with related practices around disease prevention, hygiene standards, observation, and care-taking

Facilitate reduction in AMU through grants and low-interest loans for infrastructure. Educational and promotional efforts to reduce antimicrobial use could target farms which are undergoing significant changes

Broaden the idea of who is a farmer concerning advice and support for antimicrobial use reduction

Decisions on the administration of antimicrobials may be made by farm staff or family members rather than the 'primary farmer'. Calf rearers, in particular, are often women.

Ensure that advice and support on antimicrobial use is targeted to both the farm decision-maker (who decides whether antimicrobial use is an option) and the person who administers the antimicrobials (who determines on whether to use antimicrobials in a specific instance).

Be sensitive to gender and develop training which is accessible to women.

Trigger change in AMU

Key moments of change on a farm (e.g. succession, major disease outbreaks, farm accidents, new infrastructure construction, economic failure) lead to farming system changes which can include AMU.

Link information on reducing antimicrobial use to broader on-farm hygiene practices, efficiencies or transition to lower input production.

Change broader production practices

Changes to farm infrastructure can reduce antimicrobial use while increasing production efficiency.

Regulate the circulation of marginal livestock (e.g. calves) to reduce vulnerabilities.

Increase quality controls in the supply and care of young animals to reduce the need for AMU.

Work with the agrifood supply chain

Procurement standards can have a major impact on AMU.

Encourage supply chain actors to include restrictions on antimicrobial use in farmer contracts

www.roadmap-h2020.eu

The ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 817626.

ARMOR

